

"RESPONSE OF BIOSTIMULANT APPLICATION ON NUTRIENT UPTAKE, WATER PRODUCTIVITY AND ECONOMIC VIABILITY IN WHEAT CULTIVATION"

A.S. Giramkar¹, D.D. Khedkar², M.S. Mane³, S.K. Ghodke⁴, B.M. Bhalerao⁵, A.P. Bhojar⁶

- 1) M.sc. Student, Inter faculty Department of Irrigation water management, Mahatma Phule Krishi Vidyapeeth, Rahuri (MH) India.
- 2) Associate professor, Inter faculty Department of Irrigation water management, Mahatma Phule Krishi Vidyapeeth, Rahuri (MH) India.
- 3) Associate Dean, College of Agriculture Pune. Mahatma Phule Krishi Vidyapeeth, Rahuri (MH) India.
- 4) Assistant professor, Department of Soil Science, Mahatma Phule Krishi Vidyapeeth, Rahuri (MH) India.
- 5) Associate professor, Department of Biochemistry, Mahatma Phule Krishi Vidyapeeth, Rahuri (MH) India.
- 6) Ph.D. Scholar, Department of Agricultural Economics Mahatma Phule Krishi Vidyapeeth, Rahuri (MH) India.

aagiramkar111@gmail.com

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Abstract

The study, "Response of Biostimulant Application on Nutrient Uptake, Water Productivity and Economic Viability in Wheat Cultivation", investigates the influence of biostimulant treatments on wheat (*Triticum aestivum* L.) cultivated under drip irrigation. The research examines key parameters, including nutrient uptake, water use efficiency (WUE), and economic returns. This field experiment was conducted during the 2023-24 Rabi season at the experimental farm of Mahatma Phule Krishi Vidyapeeth, Rahuri, located in a semi-arid, subtropical zone. The area received an average annual rainfall of 520 mm, mostly during the southwest monsoon, with erratic distribution. A randomized block design (RBD) was employed with 14 treatments with three replications in randomized block design. Grain yield peaked at 49.29 q ha⁻¹ in T₁₀, significantly exceeding other treatments with similar trends observed for straw yield. Drip irrigation was used for irrigation. The first irrigation was applied immediately after sowing to ensure proper germination, followed by irrigation on alternate days throughout the crop's growth period. The results reveal that the highest WUE (18.26 kg ha⁻¹ mm⁻¹) was achieved by T₁₀ treatment, combining 100% RD of NPK and two foliar sprays of biostimulant powder (3 g L⁻¹), alongside the highest nutrient uptake for nitrogen (114.21 kg ha⁻¹), phosphorus (33.10 kg ha⁻¹), and potassium (97.57 kg ha⁻¹). Economic analysis demonstrated that this treatment also delivered the highest gross monetary returns (₹1,35,929 ha⁻¹), net monetary returns (₹80,831 ha⁻¹), and B:C ratio (2.47). The findings underscore the potential of biostimulants in enhancing nutrient efficiency, conserving water, and increasing economic viability in wheat production, offering a sustainable alternative to traditional agricultural practices.

Keywords: Wheat, Biostimulant, Nutrient Uptake, Water use efficiency, Gross Returns, B:C ratio.

Introduction

Wheat (*Triticum aestivum* L.) is a widely cultivated cereal grain and a key staple food globally, known for its higher protein content compared to other major cereals. Belonging to the family "Poaceae" and genus "Triticum," wheat has a chromosome number of 2n = 42 and is often referred to as the "king of cereals." It originated in Southwestern Asia, specifically in Turkey, and was introduced to India by the Aryans.

India cultivates three main species of wheat: *Triticum aestivum*, *Triticum durum*, and *Triticum dicocum* L. Botanically, the wheat kernel is classified as a caryopsis, a type of fruit. Wheat is the second most important staple food in India after rice. It is composed of 10–12% protein, 57% carbohydrates, and 2–4% lysine, and serves as a rich source of thiamine, nicotinic acid, and other B-vitamins. Its protein contains gluten, a unique component that provides elasticity and sponginess to bread, making it essential for baking.

In India, wheat is traditionally cultivated during the rabi season. It thrives in regions with an annual rainfall of 700–1600 mm. Optimal conditions for wheat cultivation include winter temperatures of 10°C–15°C and summer temperatures ranging from 21°C to 26°C. Water is critical throughout the plant's life cycle, from seed germination to maturity, to achieve high yields. Wheat requires approximately 55–60 days of a cool climate during its early growth stages. The ideal soil pH for wheat ranges from 6.5 to 7.5.

Wheat sowing typically begins in September-October in states like Karnataka, Maharashtra, Andhra Pradesh, Madhya Pradesh, Punjab, Haryana, and Rajasthan. In contrast, in Himachal Pradesh and Jammu & Kashmir, sowing generally takes place in November-December. During the 2017-2018 season, India's wheat production declined by 1.40 million tonnes, reaching 97.11 million tonnes, compared to a record 98.51 million tonnes in the previous year. In Maharashtra, wheat is cultivated on over 20 lakh hectares, representing 4.5% of the total cultivated area in the country (Anonymous 2017-2018).

Biostimulants that are enhanced with fulvic and humic acids are becoming important instruments for improving soil fertility and wheat growth. These compounds enhance microbial activity, water retention, nutrient chelation, and plant resistance to abiotic stressors. Foliar application of biostimulants (Delfine et al. 2005; Muhammad et al. 2019; Yadav *et.al.*, 2021) has proven particularly effective, as it delivers nutrients directly to leaves, ensuring rapid absorption and minimizing dependence on soil conditions. By improving plant health and lowering the need for synthetic fertilisers, organic formulations made from fermented materials, such as panchagavya and jeevamrut, also promote sustainable agriculture. Biostimulants provide a sustainable solution to problems in wheat cultivation, like limited nutrient availability and environmental stresses, by increasing crop performance and nutrient efficiency. (Yaseen, et al., 2011)

Material and Methods

Chemical Studies

Soil samples were collected from the experimental field at a depth of 0-20 cm both initially and after harvest. These samples were thoroughly mixed, air-dried in the shade, ground using a mortar and pestle, and passed through a 2 mm sieve. The available nitrogen, phosphorus, and potassium content were analysed using established standard procedures.

Plant analysis

The wheat crop grown under observation was collected at harvest for chemical analysis. The plant samples were initially sun-dried and then oven-dried at 65°C until a constant weight was achieved. The dried samples were then ground into a fine powder and used to analyse the total nitrogen, phosphorus, and potassium content. Standard methods were employed to determine the nutrient content in the plant samples at harvest.

Nutrient uptake

Following formula was used to calculate the nutrient uptake

$$\text{Dry matter accumulation (kg ha}^{-1}\text{)} \times \text{Nutrient content (\%)} = \text{Uptake of nutrients (kg ha}^{-1}\text{)}$$

$$\text{Uptake of nutrients (kg ha}^{-1}\text{)} = \frac{\text{Dry matter accumulation (kg ha}^{-1}\text{)} \times \text{Nutrient content (\%)}}{100}$$

Irrigation Studies

Water was supplied to the wheat crop using a climatological approach via a drip irrigation system. Irrigation was scheduled to occur every

other day through the drip system. The specifications and details of the drip irrigation setup were recorded

Sr. No.	Particular	Size or Specifications
1.	Type of main and sub main	Poly-vinyl chloride (PVC)
2.	Type of laterals	Low Density Polyethylene (LDPE)
3.	Size of main	63mm
4.	Size of sub main	40 mm
5.	Size of laterals	16 mm
6.	Type of dripper	Inline dripper
7.	Discharge of emitter	4 lph
8.	Number of laterals plot ⁻¹	2
9.	Spacing between emitters	0.50 m
10.	Spacing between laterals	1.2 m

The reference crop evapotranspiration (ET₀) was calculated using the Penman-Monteith method recommended by FAO-56, based on a climatological approach. The irrigation water depth to be applied was determined using the appropriate formula.

$$ET_C = K_C \times ET_0$$

Where,

ET_C = Evapotranspiration of crop (mm)

K_C = Crop coefficient values

ET₀ = Reference evapotranspiration (mm)

The volume of water required at alternate days can be

$$d \times A \times W_a$$

$$V = \frac{\text{---}}{E_u}$$

Where,

V = Volume of water to be applied (Liter per plot)

d = Depth of water to be applied (mm)

A = Area of 2 strips (2 pairs) to be irrigated (m²)

W_a = Wetted area, 50 %

E_u = Emission uniformity

The operating time of system (t) was calculated by

$$V \times 60$$

$$t = \frac{\text{---}}{Q \times N_e}$$

Where,

t = Operating time of system (hr)

V = Volume of water to be applied (lit plot⁻¹)

Q = Average emitter discharge (lph)

N_e = Number of drippers per plot

The relationship between crop yield and total water consumption during crop growth is known as water productivity. Thus, the following formula was used to calculate the water productivity.

$$\text{Yield}$$

$$WP = \frac{\text{---}}{\text{Water applied to the field}}$$

Economics

The B:C ratio, cultivation costs, net and gross financial returns, and other economic studies of rabi wheat were calculated. The price of growing. Data on a number of factors, including wages, the rate of hired labour, seed costs, fertiliser market rates, plant protection measures, machinery costs, irrigation costs, and interest on working capital, were used to estimate the cost of growing wheat. The total cost of cultivation took into account the input price (₹ ha⁻¹).

Gross Monetary Returns

Gross monetary returns for each treatment were calculated by multiplying the yield by the prevailing market price of wheat (₹ per

quintal).

Net Monetary Returns

Net monetary returns for each treatment were determined by deducting the cost of cultivation from the gross monetary returns.

Benefit-Cost Ratio (B:C Ratio)

The B:C ratio was calculated by dividing the gross monetary returns by the total cost of cultivation for the respective treatment.

$$\text{Gross monetary returns (₹ ha}^{-1}\text{)}$$

$$\text{B:C Ratio} = \frac{\text{---}}{\text{---}}$$

$$\text{Cost of cultivation (₹ ha}^{-1}\text{)}$$

For statistical analysis, a standard analysis of variance (ANOVA) method was applied to assess the data based on the Randomized Block Design (RBD). The "F" test of significance was employed to evaluate the null hypothesis, and the corresponding standard error (SE) for each treatment effect was calculated. The critical difference (C.D.) at the 5% level of significance was determined to identify significant differences.

Result And Discussion

Irrigation Studies

The data on total water applied and water use efficiency is presented. The average water requirement for the wheat crop under drip irrigation was 270 mm, which is the lowest compared to the surface irrigation method. Water usage in drip irrigation is significantly lower than in surface irrigation, as water is applied at a slower rate over an extended period directly to the plant's root zone through a low-pressure delivery system. This method enhances the availability of nutrients near the roots while reducing leaching losses. It also promotes better water utilization, improved nutrient uptake, reduced salt accumulation in the root zone, and maintains optimal soil-water-air relationships, with increased oxygen levels in the root zone, keeping soil moisture levels stable.

Yield

The observed mean wheat grain yield was 43.60 q ha⁻¹. The treatment involving 100% RD of NPK combined with two foliar sprays of Biostimulant Powder at 3 g L⁻¹ (T₁₀) produced the highest grain yield of 49.29 q ha⁻¹, significantly surpassing other treatments. However, this was statistically comparable to 100% RD of NPK with two foliar sprays of Biostimulant Powder at 2 g L⁻¹ (T₉), yielding 48.02 q ha⁻¹ and with Biostimulant Liquid at 6 ml L⁻¹ (T₁₃), yielding 47.68 q ha⁻¹. The highest percentage increase in yield 19.05%, was observed in T₁₀, followed by 15.99% in T₉, compared to the control treatment (T₂). The lowest grain yield of 27.49 q ha⁻¹ was recorded in the untreated control (T₁). The increased yield can be attributed to the role of biostimulants in enhancing physiological functions such as chlorophyll production, enzyme activity, and nutrient translocation, which contribute to better grain development. Similarly, the straw yield showed a mean of 59.90 q ha⁻¹, with T₁₀ again achieving the maximum yield of 68.22 q ha⁻¹,

closely followed by T₉ and T₁₃. The untreated control (T₁) recorded the lowest straw yield of 38.24 q ha⁻¹, reflecting inadequate nutrient availability. These findings suggest that the application of foliar biostimulants at critical growth stages significantly improves both grain and straw yields in wheat.

Water Use Efficiency (WUE)

The data on WUE, influenced by various treatments, is presented in Table. Water use efficiency (WUE) can be improved by either increasing the numerator (crop yield) or decreasing the denominator. The numerator, representing plant production, is influenced by factors such as plant growth enhancement through photosynthesis and losses due to pests and diseases. Therefore, WUE can be affected by pest and

disease control, as well as the availability and uptake of nutrients.

The highest Water Use Efficiency value, 18.26 kg ha⁻¹mm⁻¹ was observed in the treatment involving 100% Recommended Dose (RD) of NPK + two foliar sprays of Biostimulant Powder at 3 g L⁻¹ (T₁₀), followed by 100% RD of NPK + two foliar sprays of Biostimulant Powder at 2 g L⁻¹ (T₉), with a WUE of 17.79 kg ha⁻¹mm⁻¹.

The lowest WUE was recorded in T₁, the control treatment with 0% RD of NPK, at 10.18 kg ha⁻¹mm⁻¹. There was a noticeable percentage of water savings in drip-irrigated treatments compared to surface-irrigated treatments. The saved water can not only increase the area that can be irrigated but also result in significant yield improvements through drip irrigation.

Table 1.1: Total water applied and water use efficiency (WUE) of wheat influenced by different treatments

Sr. No.	Treatments	Total Water Applied (mm)	Yield (q ha ⁻¹)	WUE (kg ha ⁻¹ mm)
T ₁	Control 0% RD of NPK	270	27.49	10.18
T ₂	100 % RD of NPK.	270	41.40	15.33
T ₃	100 % RD of NPK + SD with BP @ 1 g L ⁻¹	270	42.86	15.87
T ₄	100 % RD of NPK + SD with BL @ 1 ml L ⁻¹	270	43.14	15.98
T ₅	100 % RD of NPK + BA of BP @ 1.25 kg ha ⁻¹	270	44.08	16.33
T ₆	100 % RD of NPK + BA of BP @ 1.90 kg ha ⁻¹	270	44.28	16.40
T ₇	100 % RD of NPK + BA of BP @ 2.5 kg ha ⁻¹	270	44.45	16.46
T ₈	100 % RD of NPK + Two foliar sprays of BP @ 1g L ⁻¹	270	46.73	17.31
T ₉	100 % RD of NPK + Two foliar sprays of BP @ 2g L ⁻¹	270	48.02	17.79
T ₁₀	100 % RD of NPK + Two foliar sprays of BP @3g L ⁻¹	270	49.29	18.26
T ₁₁	100 % RD of NPK + Two foliar sprays of BL @ 2ml L ⁻¹	270	45.14	16.62
T ₁₂	100 % RD of NPK + Two foliar sprays of BL @ 4 ml L ⁻¹	270	45.15	16.72
T ₁₃	100 % RD of NPK + Two foliar sprays of BL @ 6 ml L ⁻¹	270	47.68	17.66
T ₁₄	75 % RD of NPK + BA of BP @ 1.25 kg ha ⁻¹ + Two foliar spray of BL @ 4 ml L ⁻¹	270	40.97	15.17

Soil Nutrient Analysis

The levels of nitrogen, phosphorus, and potassium in the soil of the treated wheat plots were significantly affected by the application of bio stimulants, both as a basal application and through foliar sprays. The

average concentrations of available nitrogen, phosphorus, and potassium in the soil after the harvest of wheat were 159.48, 16.44, and 351.50 kg ha⁻¹, respectively.

Table 1.2. Available NPK content in soil influenced by different treatments

Sr. No.	Treatments	Available NPK (kg ha ⁻¹) at harvest		
		Nitrogen	Phosphorus	Potassium
T ₁	Control 0% RD of NPK	148.13	13.25	339.87
T ₂	100 % RD of NPK.	163.58	18.05	354.27
T ₃	100 % RD of NPK + SD with BP @ 1 g L ⁻¹	162.72	17.47	354.08
T ₄	100 % RD of NPK + SD with BL @ 1 ml L ⁻¹	162.43	17.38	353.89
T ₅	100 % RD of NPK + BA of BP @ 1.25 kg ha ⁻¹	161.95	17.28	353.79
T ₆	100 % RD of NPK + BA of BP @ 1.90 kg ha ⁻¹	161.57	17.18	353.50
T ₇	100 % RD of NPK + BA of BP @ 2.5 kg ha ⁻¹	160.13	16.61	352.64
T ₈	100 % RD of NPK + Two foliar sprays of BP @ 1g L ⁻¹	160.42	16.99	353.12
T ₉	100 % RD of NPK + Two foliar sprays of BP @ 2g L ⁻¹	159.36	15.94	351.01
T ₁₀	100 % RD of NPK + Two foliar sprays of BP @3g L ⁻¹	158.78	15.55	350.43
T ₁₁	100 % RD of NPK + Two foliar sprays of BL @ 2ml L ⁻¹	160.22	16.90	352.93
T ₁₂	100 % RD of NPK + Two foliar sprays of BL @ 4 ml L ⁻¹	159.94	16.32	352.45
T ₁₃	100 % RD of NPK + Two foliar sprays of BL @ 6 ml L ⁻¹	159.65	16.22	351.20
T ₁₄	75 % RD of NPK + BA of BP @ 1.25 kg ha ⁻¹ + Two foliar spray of BL @ 4 ml L ⁻¹	153.79	15.07	347.84
	General Mean	159.48	16.44	351.50
	S.E. ±	0.11	0.03	0.20
	CD at 5%	0.34	0.08	0.59

The availability of NPK was found to be significantly influenced by the different treatments applied. The highest availability of NPK at harvest (163.58, 18.05, and 354.27 kg ha⁻¹, respectively) was recorded in the treatment with 100% RD of NPK (T₂), outperforming all other

treatments. In contrast, the control treatment with no NPK fertilizer (T₁) showed the lowest availability of nitrogen, phosphorus, and potassium, with values of 148.13, 13.25, and 339.87 kg ha⁻¹,

respectively, at harvest. (Khattak et al. 2017; Merwad 2019; Vikas et al. 2019; Kumar Sootahar et al. 2020).

Availability of Nitrogen in Soil

The availability of nitrogen in the root zone soil of wheat was found to be influenced by both the duration and levels of fertilizer application. The data on nitrogen availability in the soil, as affected by different treatments. The average available nitrogen content in the soil after the wheat harvest was 159.48 kg ha⁻¹. At harvest, the treatment with 100% RD of NPK (T₂) recorded a significantly higher nitrogen availability of 163.58 kg ha⁻¹. This increase may be attributed to its relatively lower nitrogen uptake compared to other treatments (Khattak et al. 2017; Merwad 2019; Vikas et al. 2019; Kumar Sootahar et al. 2020).

Availability of Phosphorus in Soil

The data on phosphorus availability in the soil, influenced by various treatments. The availability of phosphorus in the root zone soil was found to be affected by both the duration and levels of fertilizer application. The average available phosphorus content in the soil after the wheat harvest was 16.44 kg ha⁻¹. At harvest, the treatment with 100% RD of NPK (T₂) showed significantly higher phosphorus availability (18.05 kg ha⁻¹), which may be due to its relatively lower uptake of the nutrient compared to other treatments (Izhar Shafi et al. 2020; Kumar Sootahar et al. 2020).

Availability of Potassium in Soil

The average available potassium content in the soil after the wheat harvest was 451.50 kg ha⁻¹. The availability of potassium in the root zone soil was found to be impacted by the duration and levels of fertilizer application. At harvest, the treatment with 100% RD of NPK (T₂) showed significantly higher potassium availability (354.27 kg

ha⁻¹), likely due to its relatively lower potassium uptake compared to other treatments (Surve and Bhosale 2015).

Plant Nutrient Uptake

The data on the total nutrient uptake influenced by different treatments. The average nitrogen, phosphorus, and potassium uptake by wheat were 97.50, 28.20, and 83.60 kg ha⁻¹, respectively. The uptake of total nutrients (NPK) was significantly affected by the different treatments applied. The highest uptake of nitrogen, phosphorus, and potassium was 114.21, 33.10, and 97.57 kg ha⁻¹, respectively. It was recorded in the treatment involving 100% RD of NPK + two foliar sprays of Biostimulant Powder at 3 g L⁻¹ (T₁₀). However, this was similar to the results observed in the treatments with 100% RD of NPK + two foliar sprays of Biostimulant Powder at 2 g L⁻¹ (T₉) and 100% RD of NPK + two foliar sprays of Biostimulant Liquid at 6 ml L⁻¹ (T₁₃). The control treatment, with no NPK fertilizer (T₁), resulted in the lowest nutrient uptake for N, P, and K, with values of 57.23, 15.46, and 50.51 kg ha⁻¹, respectively, at harvest (Eshwar et al. 2017; Das et al. 2020; Rajaie 2022).

Total Nitrogen Uptake

The highest total nitrogen uptake (114.21 kg ha⁻¹) was observed in the treatment with 100% RD of NPK + two foliar sprays of Biostimulant Powder at 3 g L⁻¹ (T₁₀), which was significantly higher than all other treatments. However, this result was comparable to the treatments with 100% RD of NPK + two foliar sprays of Biostimulant Powder at 2 g L⁻¹ (T₉) and 100% RD of NPK + two foliar sprays of Biostimulant Liquid at 6 ml L⁻¹ (T₁₃). The increase in total nitrogen uptake in T₁₀ can likely be attributed to the improved nutrient availability in the root zone, resulting from the application of Biostimulant Powder foliar sprays at the tillering and pre-flowering stages (Eshwar et al. 2017; Das et al. 2020; Rajaie 2022).

Table 1.3. Nutrient uptake of wheat crop influenced by different treatments

Sr. No.	Treatments	Total nutrient Uptake (kg ha ⁻¹)		
		Nitrogen	Phosphorus	Potassium
T ₁	Control 0% RD of NPK	57.23	15.46	50.51
T ₂	100 % RD of NPK.	89.86	26.05	77.27
T ₃	100 % RD of NPK + SD with BP @ 1 g L ⁻¹	94.37	27.35	81.03
T ₄	100 % RD of NPK + SD with BL @ 1 ml L ⁻¹	95.23	27.60	81.75
T ₅	100 % RD of NPK + BA of BP @ 1.25 kg ha ⁻¹	98.15	28.45	84.18
T ₆	100 % RD of NPK + BA of BP @ 1.90 kg ha ⁻¹	98.76	28.63	84.70
T ₇	100 % RD of NPK + BA of BP @ 2.5 kg ha ⁻¹	99.27	28.77	85.12
T ₈	100 % RD of NPK + Two foliar sprays of BP @ 1g L ⁻¹	106.30	30.81	90.98
T ₉	100 % RD of NPK + Two foliar sprays of BP @ 2g L ⁻¹	110.29	31.97	94.30
T ₁₀	100 % RD of NPK + Two foliar sprays of BP @3g L ⁻¹	114.21	33.10	97.57
T ₁₁	100 % RD of NPK + Two foliar sprays of BL @ 2ml L ⁻¹	101.40	29.39	86.90
T ₁₂	100 % RD of NPK + Two foliar sprays of BL @ 4 ml L ⁻¹	101.43	29.40	86.92
T ₁₃	100 % RD of NPK + Two foliar sprays of BL@ 6 ml L ⁻¹	109.25	31.67	93.44
T ₁₄	75 % RD of NPK + BA of BP @ 1.25 kg ha ⁻¹ + Two foliar spray of BL @ 4 ml L ⁻¹	88.55	25.67	76.18
	General Mean	97.5	28.2	83.6
	S.E. ±	2.54	0.76	2.16
	CD at 5%	7.44	2.23	6.33

Total Phosphorus Uptake

The highest total phosphorus uptake (33.10 kg ha⁻¹) was observed in the treatment with 100% RD of NPK + two foliar sprays of Biostimulant Powder at 3 g L⁻¹ (T₁₀), which was significantly greater than other treatments. This result was comparable to the treatments involving 100% RD of NPK with two foliar sprays of Biostimulant Liquid at 2 g L⁻¹ (T₉) and 6 ml L⁻¹ (T₁₃). The increased phosphorus uptake can be attributed to the enhanced nutrient availability through biostimulant application at key growth stages (Izhar Shafi et al. 2020).

Total Potassium Uptake

The data on total potassium uptake by the wheat crop, as shown in Table., revealed that potassium plays a crucial role in water movement, nutrient distribution, and carbohydrate processing in plants, which directly influences yield. The highest potassium uptake (97.57 kg ha⁻¹) was recorded in the treatment with 100% RD of NPK + two foliar sprays of Biostimulant Powder at 3 g L⁻¹ (T₁₀), followed by similar results in T₉ and T₁₃. These findings align with the research (Surve and Bhosale 2015).

Economics

Cost of Cultivation

The cost of cultivating wheat was affected by the application of various biostimulant treatments. The highest cultivation cost was observed with the treatment of 100% RD of NPK + two foliar sprays of Biostimulant Liquid at 6 ml L⁻¹ (T₁₃), amounting to ₹55,349 per

hectare, followed by the treatment with 100% RD of NPK + two foliar sprays of Biostimulant Powder at 3 g L⁻¹ (T₁₀), which cost ₹55,098 per hectare. The lowest cost of cultivation was recorded in the control treatment (T₁), at ₹42,415 per hectare.

Table 1.4. Gross monetary returns, Cost of cultivation, Net monetary returns and B:C ratio of wheat as influenced by different treatments

Sr. No.	Treatments	Cost of cultivation (₹ ha ⁻¹)	Gross monetary return (₹ ha ⁻¹)	Net monetary return (₹ ha ⁻¹)	B:C ratio
T ₁	Control 0% RD of NPK	42415	75835	33420	1.79
T ₂	100 % RD of NPK.	52076	114022	61946	2.19
T ₃	100 % RD of NPK + SD with BP @ 1 g L ⁻¹	52812	118851	66039	2.25
T ₄	100 % RD of NPK + SD with BL @ 1 ml L ⁻¹	52874	118076	65202	2.23
T ₅	100 % RD of NPK + BA of BP @ 1.25 kg ha ⁻¹	53674	121480	67806	2.26
T ₆	100 % RD of NPK + BA of BP @ 1.90 kg ha ⁻¹	54151	122033	67882	2.25
T ₇	100 % RD of NPK + BA of BP @ 2.5 kg ha ⁻¹	54627	122490	67863	2.24
T ₈	100 % RD of NPK + Two foliar sprays of BP @ 1g L ⁻¹	54223	128813	74590	2.38
T ₉	100 % RD of NPK + Two foliar sprays of BP @ 2g L ⁻¹	54655	131466	76811	2.41
T ₁₀	100 % RD of NPK + Two foliar sprays of BP @3g L ⁻¹	55098	135929	80831	2.47
T ₁₁	100 % RD of NPK + Two foliar sprays of BL @ 2ml L ⁻¹	54187	124407	70220	2.30
T ₁₂	100 % RD of NPK + Two foliar sprays of BL @ 4 ml L ⁻¹	54782	124429	69647	2.27
T ₁₃	100 % RD of NPK + Two foliar sprays of BL@ 6 ml L ⁻¹	55349	132401	77052	2.39
T ₁₄	75 % RD of NPK + BA of BP @ 1.25 kg ha ⁻¹ + Two foliar spray of BL @ 4 ml L ⁻¹	53333	112846	33420	1.79
	General Mean	53161	120220	67059	2.30
	S.E. ±	-	2307.59	2307.59	-
	CD at 5%	-	6768.33	6768.33	-

The highest gross monetary returns of ₹1,35,929 per hectare were observed in the treatment with 100% RD of NPK + two foliar sprays of Biostimulant Powder at 3 g L⁻¹ (T₁₀), followed by treatments with 100% RD of NPK + two foliar sprays of Biostimulant Liquid at 6 ml L⁻¹ (T₁₃) ₹1,32,405 and 100% RD of NPK + two foliar sprays of Biostimulant Powder at 2 g L⁻¹ (T₉) ₹1,31,466. The lowest gross returns (₹75,835) were recorded in the control treatment (T₁). The increase in gross returns can be attributed to higher yields from the biostimulant treatments. For net monetary returns, T₁₀ recorded the highest value of ₹80,831 per hectare, closely followed by T₉ (₹76,811) and T₁₃ (₹77,052), while the control treatment had the lowest return (₹33,420). In terms of B:C ratio, T₁₀ showed the highest ratio of 2.47, followed by T₉ (2.41). The control treatment had the lowest B:C ratio of 1.38 (Muhammad Khan et al. 2010; Ahmad Khan et al. 2018).

Summary and conclusion

The wheat crop was irrigated using drip irrigation, with an average water requirement of 270 mm, which was lower compared to the surface irrigation method. The highest water use efficiency (WUE) of 18.26 kg ha⁻¹ mm⁻¹ was observed in treatment T₁₀ (100% RD of NPK + Two foliar sprays of Biostimulant Powder @ 3 g L⁻¹), followed by T₉ (17.79 kg ha⁻¹ mm⁻¹) and T₁₃ (17.66 kg ha⁻¹ mm⁻¹). The control treatment (T₁) recorded the lowest WUE (10.18 kg ha⁻¹ mm⁻¹).

Soil analysis showed that the highest available nitrogen, phosphorus, and potassium were recorded in the 100% RD of NPK treatment (T₂), with values of 163.58 kg ha⁻¹, 18.05 kg ha⁻¹, and 354.27 kg ha⁻¹, respectively. The control treatment had the lowest nutrient availability. In terms of nutrient uptake, treatment T₁₀ had the highest total nitrogen uptake (114.21 kg ha⁻¹), followed by T₉ and T₁₃. Similarly, the highest phosphorus (33.10 kg ha⁻¹) and potassium (97.57 kg ha⁻¹) uptakes were also observed in T₁₀, with T₉ and T₁₃ being comparable.

Regarding the economics, the highest gross monetary returns of ₹1,35,929 ha⁻¹ were recorded in T₁₀, followed by T₁₃. The highest net monetary returns (₹80,831 ha⁻¹) and B:C ratio (2.47) were also observed in T₁₀.

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